

Teachers' Perception and The Teaching of National Languages and Cultures in English Primary Schools in Douala IV Sub- Division, Littoral Region of Cameroon

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Abstract

This study sought to investigate the effects of teachers' perceptions on the teaching of National languages and Cultures in English Primary schools in Douala IV Sub-Division. Specifically, the study sought to find out the effects of teachers' attitudes, teachers' knowledge and teachers' beliefs on the teaching of National Languages and Cultures. Three research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Related literature was reviewed alongside theoretical framework and empirical reviews. The convergent parallel mixed method research design was employed and a sample size of 69 teachers was drawn from 12 public English primary schools in Douala IV Sub-Division. The instruments for data collection were questionnaires and interview guide designed for teachers. Quantitative data was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. A pre-design EpiData version 3.1 database which has in-built consistency and validation checks were used to enter the data. Further, to ensure consistency, data range and validation checks were performed in SPSS version 25.0 to identify invalid codes. Frequencies and percentages were used for descriptive statistics. The descriptive data were further used to verify the hypotheses that were stated in the study. The spearman's rho correlation test was used to verify the effects of teachers' perceptions on the teaching of National Languages and Cultures in English Primary schools in Douala IV Sub-Division. Qualitative data was analyzed using thematic analyses with the aid of themes, groundings and quotations. The findings revealed that there was a positive correlation between teachers' attitudes and the teaching of National Languages and Cultures, (78.1%), ($r=0.347^{**}$, $n=60$), $p<0.05$. It was equally revealed that there was positive correlation between teachers' knowledge and the teaching of National Languages and Cultures, (78.3%), ($r=0.242^{**}$, $n=60$, $p<.05$). Finally, findings revealed that teachers' beliefs have significant positive effects on the teaching of National Languages and Cultures in English Primary schools in Douala IV Sub-Division, (71.4 %), ($r=.903^{**}$, $n=60$ $p<.05$). It was concluded that teachers' perceptions have a significant effect on the teaching of National Languages and Cultures in English Primary schools in Douala IV Sub-Division. The researcher recommended that the educational authorities should organize and sponsor development programs that will boost the teachers' knowledge of National Languages and Cultures in order for them to teach this subject effectively.

Keywords: Teachers' Perceptions, Teachers' Attitudes, Teachers' Knowledge, Teachers' Beliefs and National Languages and Cultures.

Introduction

Language is an important aspect of culture as it stands as a medium of transmission of cultural values, knowledge and skills from one generation to another. Culture is broad and can be learned in different ways. While other aspects of culture can easily be learned through observation and imitation, language learning is a gradual process which requires competent personnel to enable learners develop language skills. For this reason, this work dwelled much on national languages than cultures.

The importance of national languages in Cameroon cannot be underestimated. One's native language is his cultural identity. National languages also called indigenous languages or mother tongue or native languages are the means through which cultural norms values and traditions are transmitted from one generation to another. National Languages and Cultures (NLCs) is a subject that teaches the various indigenous languages of Cameroon and their cultures in Primary schools. This subject was introduced in the primary school curriculum in 2018 with aim to promote national cultures. A majority of national languages in Africa risk disappearing (United national 2019) and Cameroonian languages are not left out. An enormous number of children in Cameroon cannot express themselves in any national language most especially those who are born and bred in cities like Douala and Yaoundé where French language seems to dominate other languages including in English language. Television programs that attract children are either in English or in French. English and French are the only languages of instruction in Cameroon schools and most parents prefer that their children should learn only official languages in order to overcome the inferiority complex in which Africans feel that the white man is superior as well as his language. Parents also believe that English and French opens children to the world. The introduction of NLCs into the primary school curriculum marked a strong foundation for the promotion of cultures and enhancement of a strong sense of identity, helps in the overall development of the child, build a foundation to the learning other languages and enable them to communicate with other members of the community.

Effective teaching depends on the teachers' perception of the subject amongst other factors. The attitude, knowledge and beliefs of a teacher in regards to NLCs may influence his teaching of that subject. Poor attitude, negative beliefs and poor knowledge may lead to ineffective teaching meanwhile positive attitude, positive beliefs and high knowledge may produce effective teaching and hence high performance. The scarcity of information on the teachers' perceptions of NLCs is regrettable because it stands as a guide for sensitization or creation of awareness on the effect of their perceptions on the teaching of this subject. This study thus aimed at investigating the effects of teachers' perceptions on the teaching of National Languages and Cultures in English Primary schools in Douala IV Sub-Division.

Understanding The Importance of National Languages within the context of Cameroon

As well as being a system of written or oral expression used by a group of people to communicate, language is both a main cultural object and the condition for expression of culture. It is considered the vehicle of identity values that are indicators of practices or reveals the habits and customs of a people or a community. In other words, it is the liveliest expression of a people's autonomy and heritage (Fomekong, Teko & Temotio 2023).

A national language is the language of a political, cultural, and education unit (Alexander, 2003). It is used to identify the nation and unite its people of that nation. Having a national language has a lot of importance. Language is not for show but meant to be useful to its people. We need a common language so that most of us can understand others view points and may readily cooperate. National language is the driving force of National unity of a people and make them distinct from other people. National languages are very important for economic productivity (Chiatot & Akumbu, 2013). When people speak the same language, they feel as one people and this enhances the spirit of working together and hence increases productivity.

Moreover, language has an educational value. All modern knowledge, skills and knowhow are ideally transmitted through the educational system. Given the importance of indigenous languages in the enhancement of learning, it is clear that the strongest foundation for quality education lies in a system founded on the indigenous values, that is, languages and knowledge systems of Cameroonians. In this regard, research informs us that learning is greatly facilitated when instructions take place in languages that learners master best that is their tongue, (UNESCO, 1953; Obanya 2004). These mother tongues are indigenous languages for a vast majority of Cameroonians. National languages are reservoirs for cultural values, traditions and norms. Every single individual, community or nation is concerned with issues of identity and belonging. Our identity is essentially embedded in the languages that we speak. Since it takes individuals to build a community and a community to build a nation, it is therefore incumbent on us to carefully consider the role of indigenous languages in the construction of our national identity.

In Africa, culture is transmitted as a result of socialization process (Fafunwa 2021) as cited by Idang (2015). He further explains that a child grows into and within the cultural heritage of his people. He is not taught but catches it through observing and imitating the actions of parents and elderly siblings. He watches the naming ceremony, religious services, marriage rituals, funeral obsequies. He witnesses the coronation of a king or chief, annual festival, annual dances and so on. The child in a traditional society cannot escape his cultural and physical environment. Culture can be classified into two aspects; the material and non-material cultures the material culture includes visible tactiles, while non-material culture includes norms and mores of people. Material culture includes artefacts and craft while non-material culture is abstract but have persuasive influences on the lives of the people of a particular culture. Examples of non-material culture includes beliefs about what is good and what is bad, norms, taboos etc (Idang 2015).

The grassland people are the Bantu ethnic group made up of the Bamelike people, the Bamun, the Bamenda people and part of the south west people. They are found in the west, north west and south west regions of Cameroon. This area is famous for their architecture. They build stilt house (Takombang) and equally known for their beautiful great shows and festival such as the Ngouon festival in Foumban, the Ngonso in Nso and many others. The Bamelike culture is characterized by a complex social hierarchy with chiefs and notables holding position of authority. Bamelike people believe so much in their ancestors that they worship their skulls and offer sacrifices to them.

In terms of arts and craftsmanship, the grassfield people are renowned for their exceptional art and craftsmanship which include wood carving (e.g masks, figures etc), bamboo and rattan work, pottery, weaving (the famous grassfield cloth called the « Torghu ») etc. (Tamara 1984). In terms of music and dance, the grassfield people are known for their rhythmic music with masks and masquerades performing and traditional dances. Examples of traditional dances include, « bottle dance of the Mankon people, the Bamoun dance etc. (Tchoumbo 2001). In terms of social organization, the grass field have a complex social organizational structure with chiefdoms and fondons, we have the Mamoun chiefdom, the Nso Fondom, the Oku and Nkwen Fondoms etc. The chief and fons are at the top of the organization assisted by notables and other title holders. They carry out traditional rites and settle disputes among other duties (Nkui 1985).

According to Abdouramane, Ngum & Shi, (2022) the typical Cameroon dishes for grass field are achu and yellow soap, fufu and « kati-kati ». This is particularly for the north west region while koki is particular of the west region of Cameroon. There is Kwacoco and Epkwang common with the south westerners. Their oral literature is rich with stories, proverbs and myths that reflect their history, values and belief. They also have a strong sense of community spirit.

The Sawa people (people of the water) belong to the Bantu people and are in the Atlantic coast and in several other African countries (Neba 1997). Their culture is deeply influenced by the ocean and its resources. Historically the Sawa people are renowned for their maritime trade, linking them to other cultures and fostering a vibrant trading culture. They are also known for their intricate and colourful traditional costumes (Kabba Ngondo) usually worn during the celebration of their annual festival called the ngondo festival. Men tie loin with long sleeve shirts while women wear kaba and tie head scarves. This festival is celebrated every first week of December near the Wouri River and is characterized by traditional dances, songs, swimming competition etc. The event is aimed at uniting the sawa community and to seek the protection of the ancestors. In addition to Ngondo festival, several other festivals are organized in other parts of the region such as the Mpo'o festival in Edea and the Mbo'o festival in Nkongsamba. The sawa people speak mostly Duala language. The main traditional meal of the sawa people is "ndole" and "bobolo". They also have a matrilineal system where property and social status are passed down through the female lineage (Tchoumbo 2001).

The sudano- sahelian people are found in the northern regions of Cameroon. These societies are Lamidats, sultanates and chiefdoms. These societies have co-existed for hundreds of years and abide the laws of local Cameroonian administrators. The people of these regions are both Christians and Muslims and are very tolerant of each other. Traditionally, Sahelian people were nomadic pastoralists, moving their livestock across landscape in search of grazing land (Stenning 1957). They also carry out agriculture and cultivate crops like millet, ground-nuts maize etc.

They live in mud-brick houses with thatched roofs (Labadi 2001). In terms of dressing, men dress in long robes and turbans while women tie loins and head scarves (pictor 1992). In terms of music, drumming and dancing are essential for Sudano-sahelian with intricate rhythm and movement. They are also good craftsmen and known for their leather work, wood carving and pottery. In terms of traditional medicine, they are rich in herbal medicine using local plants to treat ailment. It should be noted that, cultural traditions can evolve with time and may be influenced by other external factors. Looking at the above four cultures and their uniqueness, the following common characteristics such as strong family ties fostering a sense of belonging, respect for traditional customs and beliefs, artistic expression, adaptability and resilience in the face of historical and environmental challenges.

The Cameroon language policy under went changes from the time that the German annexed Cameroon till the 1998 law. During the German colonial era (1884-1916), the colonial administrators encouraged the use of German language although the German missionaries and the American presbyterian missionaries preferred indigenous languages like the Basaa, the Bulu, Duala, Ewondo and Mungaka for teaching and evangelism (Mbuagbaw 2000, pg. 135). The French colonial rule imposed the use of French language as language of instruction (Stumpf 1976, Bitja'a, Kody 1999) while the British colonial rule used English language, pidgin English and some indigenous languages in school (like Bafut, Duala and Mungaka etc). Todd (1983 pg 163) maintains that indigenous languages were used as languages of instruction during the first four years of primary schools, while English was used during the last four years.

Nkenlifack et al (2011) proposed a modernization of teaching of National Languages and Cultures in Cameroon schools with the aid of icts in a bid to promote the country's cultural diversity and the diffusion of scientific knowledge in these languages. It proposes a multimedia educational platform, not yet available to the public for general consumption but

limits itself to presenting the input of ICTs in developing written competences in these languages without showcasing how this platform will enhance oral skills in them cognizant of the fact that not every technological device is a pedagogic tool. According to them, the use of icts stands as the best means of teaching national languages and cultures through role play, songs, numbers, arts and crafts etc. Tan (2015) enumerated some methods of teaching culture in a language classroom such as songs, stories and some strategies such as using a resource person and using online resources. He equally mentions teaching materials such as authentic materials that natives use daily, food, artifacts etc.

Teachers' Perception and the Teaching of National Languages and Cultures

Adedigba et al (2023) carried out an investigation on teachers' perception of the role of indigenous languages for culture preservation an improved teaching and learning in Nigeria using the descriptive survey design. The sample size was 266 out 5393 primary school teachers who were randomly selected from a selected state. Findings from this study revealed that teachers consider indigenous languages as a powerful tool for cultural preservation. They also held the view that indigenous languages support effective teaching and learning as when the indigenous languages are used in teaching and learning, learners are more likely to have a better and deeper understanding of what is taught than when they are taught using foreign languages.

Becerra-lubies (2022) carried out another investigation on the perception of traditional educators on the teaching of indigenous languages in Chile. The contents of relevant document and interviews with traditional educators from three groups of indigenous peoples (Mapuche, Aymara and Lican Antsy) who participated in the study were analyzed using a qualitative methodology. Using the critical language policies approach, the results were organized into three categories: a) perceptions of traditional educators regarding the intercultural bilingual education program, b) the relationship of traditional educators with other participants in the school system, and c) teaching strategies declared by traditional educators for teaching in the indigenous language class (sector Lengua Indigena). Findings revealed that traditional educators within the school is isolated and lacks the support of the communities and the intercultural bilingual program. This indicates a negative perception of the teaching of indigenous languages.

Hooijer & Fourie (2009) also carried out a qualitative study on teachers' perspective of multilingual classroom in a South African school. Different data collection technique were used such as semi-structured individual and group interview, classroom observation which concentrated mainly on teaching methods and language interaction within the classroom. Findings revealed that teachers found multilingual classroom both challenging and difficult. The study concluded that teachers in multilingual classrooms need support.

More so, Nchang, (2022) carried out another study on attitude and teachers' perception on the use of mother tongue in ESL classroom in Cameroon. The researcher used Triangulation, involving a variety of data sources including classroom observation, interview, focus group discussion and documentation. Data was collected from 24 primary school teachers from six purposely selected schools in Bafut. Findings revealed that teachers showed negative attitude and negative perception towards the use of mother tongue in ESL classroom.

Teachers' attitudes and the teaching of National Languages and Cultures

Adeniyi & Bello (2006) investigated teachers' attitude and student performance in indigenous languages in Lagos Nigeria. In their study they looked at the attitudes of private school teachers to the teaching of indigenous languages vis-à-vis the competence and performance of students in these indigenous languages. Their study was both comparative and correlative. Data was collected using Questionnaires, interview, a quasi-test and examination of junior/senior secondary school leaving certificates. Findings from these studies revealed that students' performances as reflected in their results do not demonstrate their competence in indigenous languages in question. They also found out that both teachers and students are instrumentally but not integratively motivated.

Also, Kouega (2008) investigated on minority language use in Cameroon and educated indigenes' attitude to their languages. The data collected were 36 –item questionnaires devised to check the context of the use of these languages. The analysis reveals, among other things that some use of the indigenous languages is reported in the homes and these languages are hardly used in the domain of education and media, especially TV and newspapers. Although these youths are themselves illiterate of their mother tongue, they are prepared to encourage their children to learn their ancestral languages and, if they happen to be rich, they will not hesitate to finance the development of these ancestral languages.

Kamau (2008) investigated the effects of teachers' attitude towards the teaching of mother tongue in in Nguni Division, Nwingi District in Kenya. He used the qualitative research design and data was collected using the questionnaires, informal interview. Observation, textbooks, non-governmental organizations documents, seminars, magazines, newspapers publications and other relevant materials. Data was analyzed using percentages. Findings revealed that most teachers especially the younger one did not like to teach the mother tongue and that mostly women among qualified teachers teach the mother tongue while the male teachers teach the upper classes where the language of communication is

Kiswahili or English language. Finding also revealed a negative attitude of parents towards the teaching of the mother tongue as they do not want their children to study the mother tongue.

Guzmam (2019), carried out an investigation of teachers' language use and attitudes towards multilingual education in primary schools. The aim of the study was to examine teachers' Linguistic Choices in the classroom and their attitude towards the three languages in educational context in Valencian community. Data was collected in three schools adopting three different language models, namely those of English-based, a Catalan-based and Spanish-based language models. Lo's (2015) observation scheme was used to analyze teachers' language use in thirty classrooms sessions. In addition, thirty teachers, ten from each language model school, answered a questionnaire and participated in semi-structured interview with the researcher. Findings from these studies show that, although teachers believe that multilingual classroom is encouraged in education, they mainly rely on one language: English in English model, Catalan on Catalan model and Spanish in Spanish model. Finally, the language model seems to play a role in teachers' attitude towards their languages and reveals the prestige of English Language as the lingua franca, the prestige of Spanish as a majority language and lack of prestige of Catalan as a minority language especially for those who do not use Catalan in education.

Teachers' knowledge and the teaching of National Languages and Cultures

In Cameroon, Shey (2019) investigated the external factors impeding the effective implementation of teaching/learning contents prescribed for National Languages at the observation sub-cycle in Cameroon secondary schools. Using the simple random sampling technique, a total of fifty teachers of national languages were investigated using a questionnaire. Both quantitative and qualitative data analysis techniques were used to analyze data. Findings revealed a number of factors most prominent of which were deficiencies in teachers pedagogical content knowledge, lack of adequate textbooks and few opportunities for teachers in-service and retraining programs.

Cheng (2017) also carried out a survey of native teachers' technical, pedagogical and content knowledge in Taiwan. 172 in-service Hakka language teachers' perception of technical, pedagogical and content knowledge. The survey framework included seven constructs: Content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, technical knowledge, pedagogic content knowledge, technical pedagogic knowledge, technical content knowledge and technical pedagogic and content knowledge. According to the results of this survey, although the native language teachers were satisfied with the technical pedagogic and content knowledge on average, they had relatively low confidence in content knowledge, technical knowledge and technical pedagogic knowledge. While the older male teachers tended to be more confident in the content knowledge, the old female were inclined to have less confidence in their technical knowledge. Teaching experience was positively related to the teachers' perceived content knowledge, pedagogic knowledge and pedagogic content knowledge.

Kidwell (2019) investigated on teaching about culture specifically on the role of culture in second language teacher education program. This was a quantitative study of one teacher education program in Indonesia. The aim of this study was to investigate novice teachers' learning about and practice for teaching culture. Data sources included interviews and lesson observation with 20 teacher educators, and interviews, lesson observations, and journal entries from 20 novice teachers who recently graduated from the program. Findings indicate that teachers have few opportunities to learn about how to teach about culture and that they address culture in the classrooms relatively infrequently.

Teachers' beliefs and the teaching of national languages and cultures Chou (2007) carried out an interpretive study of Han teachers' beliefs on teaching urban indigenous students in Taiwan. The study explored the beliefs and attitudes of two teachers of indigenous students by teacher educators, principals and administrators. Data was collected using qualitative research methods through classroom observation, in-depth interview and reflection logs. Data analysis identified three major themes in teachers' beliefs and attitudes of urban indigenous students: a) education for urban indigenous students, b) beliefs about indigenous students and c) beliefs about teaching. Findings indicated that teacher's experiences with cultural diversities profoundly impact their teaching practice. The more the teachers experience their student's cultures, the better they would understand and appreciate cultural diversities.

More so, Muijs & Reynolds (2002) looked at the relationship between teachers' behaviours, teacher beliefs, and teacher self-efficacy and teacher subject knowledge with student achievement in mathematics. Data was collected from 103 primary school teachers and 2148 students in UK using achievement tests, classroom observation and questionnaires. Structural equation modeling was used to test the hypothesis that all these factors would have a direct or indirect effect, with the factors most proximal to student achievement (teacher behaviour) having the strongest direct effect while more distal factor (e.g. teachers' beliefs) influencing student achievement indirectly. This hypothesis was not rejected by data. This study indicated that there is a relationship between teacher beliefs and learner's achievement.

Nkenlifack et al (2011) proposed a modernization of teaching of National Languages and Cultures in Cameroon schools with the aid of ICTs in a bid to promote the country's cultural diversity and the diffusion of scientific knowledge in these

languages. It proposes a multimedia educational platform, not yet available to the public for general consumption but limits itself to presenting the input of ICTs in developing written competences in these languages without showcasing how this platform will enhance oral skills in them cognizant of the fact that not every technological device is a pedagogic tool. According to them, the use of ICTs stands as the best means of teaching National Languages and Cultures through role play, songs, numbers, arts and crafts etc

Moreover chie (2022) carried out a study on the promotion of National languages in official sectors in Cameroon: Myth or reality? She employed the interactionist sociolinguistics theory and the language planning theory. A sample population of 120 consultants were randomly selected from a target population of 150 consultants. They were 70men and 50women between the ages of 20 to 75. The questionnaires and observation were used to collect data from both secondary and primary schools. This data was analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative methods. Findings from this study revealed that using English and French as official languages of education, communication, politics, agriculture health etc., does not allow messages to reach the entire intended audience, particularly the numerous Cameroonians who are not literate in the official languages. This study portrays that the promotion of national languages is a myth and not reality and recommends that the government should revise the language policy. This study highlights the more reason why national languages should be effectively taught in schools so that worker could express themselves in these national languages in other to better attend to those who look up to them like patients, customers etc.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on the self-perception theory of Daryl Bem 1972, the socio-cultural theory of cognitive development of Lev Vygotsky (1978), the planned behaviour theory of Ajzen (1985-1991)

The Theory of Self-perception (Daryl Bem's 1972)

This theory came up as a result of the limitations of the work of Skinner in which he analyzed that we have virtually no knowledge at all until we have been explicitly trained. To him, internal identifications that we have not been taught remain internal identifications that we cannot make. In everyday, we are spared from confronting our incompetence in this regard only because people know better than to call upon us to make internal discriminations which we are typically not taught. It also came after the cognitive dissonance theory of Festinger (1957) which postulated that “if a person hold two cognitions that are inconsistency with one another, he will experience a pressure of an aversive motivational state called cognitive dissonance, a pressure which he will seek to remove among other ways by altering one of the “dissonant” cognitions.” It was then suggested in 1965 that self-perception theory might be able to account for the major phenomena of the cognitive dissonance theory (Bem 1965).

Bem's theory of self-perception is based on two claims; firstly, the theory claims that people understand their beliefs, attitudes and perceptions by understanding their own behaviour and the circumstances surrounding it. In other words, people become aware of their inner state such as beliefs, attitude and perception by assessing their behaviours and circumstances under which the behaviors occur Bem (1972). An example is an individual who observes that he or she loves dressing in cultural regalia might infer an interest in culture. Secondly, individuals who do not have a clue of their internal states are in the same position as external observers who have external clues of their behavior to deduce or infer their internal states (Bem, 1972). In other word if an individual does not have full understanding of his behavior, he or she acts like an outsider who observes the actions and conducts and tries to make sense of it and deduce their own characteristics Mohebi & Bailey (2020).

Bem (1970 pg 8) in Mohebi & Bailey (2020), also asserts that individual's own behavior will be used by him as a source of evidence for his beliefs and attitude. For instance, a teacher's behaviour during a National Languages and Cultures can be used to infer his beliefs and attitudes towards this subject. The self-perception theory is based on the fact that people are what they do. In this sense, the relationship between self-perception and behavior are of paramount importance. The self-perception theory argues that individuals interpret their actions the same way they interpret others' actions and every individual's action is influenced by social surrounding and not by one's freewill (Bem 1972). According to Bem (1967), individuals' attitudes are developed from observing one's own behavior and making a conclusion on what attitude caused that behavior. This theory further assumes that individuals can induce attitudes without retrieving their internal state (Guadagno et al, 2010). In this theory, Bem stands out that, “when we want to know how a person feels, we look to see how he acts (Bem, 1972). Thus, self-perception theory is grounded on the premises that the overt behavior of a person is a route to find out and interpret the feelings or inner state of that person. The second postulation of self-perception suggest a partial identity between self and interpersonal perception: to the extent that internal cues are weak, ambiguous, or uninterpretable, the individual is functionally in the same position as the outside observer or an observer who will usually rely upon those same external cues to infer the individuals' inner state.

Because the self-perception theory is conceived of as a “behaviorist's” theory, it is important to emphasize that neither the interpersonal observer nor the individual himself is confined to inferences based upon overt actions only. Social

psychologists (e.g Asher 1952) have long been critical of behavioural analysis of social interactions precisely because they feel that there is something more to interpersonal relationship than responding to the overt behavior of another individual. In particular, the criticism goes that behavioural analyses failed to explicate how is it that individuals are able to account of one another's' meaning, motives, intentions and all the likes. This is explained in cases where identical behavior may have different meanings which the observer has no difficulty discerning.

Applying this theory to the teaching of National Languages and Cultures, the teacher stands a better chance to explain his or her attitudes and beliefs than an external observer, in this case the researcher. The researcher may interpret a teacher's behavior wrongly. For instance, the external observer may attribute a poorly presented lesson to the teacher's attitude towards the subject where as it could be due to other factors such as lack of knowledge of the subject matter or demotivation from the learning environment. By observing his behavior, the teacher is able to question it in order to identify what attitude is presented in that behaviour and what resulted to such a behaviour. This can help the teacher to adjust his behaviour in order to put on the one that can support leaning during a NLCs lesson. It should be noted that a teacher is able to hide his real beliefs and attitude due to the co-presence of the outside observer by acting in a completely different way from the way they would have acted if the observer was not present. This still stresses the fact that only the sincerity of teachers can reveal their perception about NLCs.

The socio-cultural theory of cognitive development (Lev Vygotsky 1978)

Lev Vygotsky was a Russian psychologist and a teacher who developed a theory about how our social interactions influence our cognitive development. The socio-cultural theory of cognitive development explores the influence that the world has on individual development. It was brought about by Lev Vygotsky in 1978 due to the limitations on the Piaget's theory of cognitive development, who believes that learners construct knowledge from the environment by themselves. Vygotsky asserted that learning is a social process whereby development occurs through interacting with people who possess more knowledge or skills than the learner.

Vygotsky sociocultural theory suggest that children internalize and learn from the beliefs and attitudes that they witness around them. He believed that culture played an important role in shaping cognitive development and therefore that this development varied across cultures. Vygotsky also stressed the importance of language as the root of all learning.

Vygotsky's sociocultural theory of human learning describes learning as a social process and the origination of human intelligence in society or culture. The major theme of Vygotsky's theoretical framework is that social interaction plays a fundamental role in the development of cognition. Vygotsky believed that everything is learned on two levels: first, through interaction with others and then integrated into the individual's cognitive structure. "Every function in the child's cultural development appears twice: Firstly, between people (inter-psychological) and then inside the child (intra-psychological). This implies equally to voluntary attention, to logical memory and to the formation of concepts.

All the higher functions originate as actual relationship between individuals. A second aspect of Vygotsky's theory is the idea that the potential for cognitive development is limited to the "Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD)". This "zone is the area of exploration for which the learner is cognitively prepared, but requires help and social interaction to fully develop. A teacher or more experience peer is able to provide the learner with what Vygotsky terms "Scaffolding" to support the learner's evolving understanding of knowledge domains or development of complex skills. Collaborative learning, discourse, modelling and scaffolding are strategies for supporting the intellectual knowledge and skills of learners and facilitating learning.

Psychologist Lev Vygotsky believed that parents, teachers, peers, care givers and society at Large influence an individual's cognitive development. He sees learning as an interactive process. Vygotsky asserted that learning was a cultural phenomenon with children from different cultures enhancing different styles of learning. According to Vygotsky, learning is a process of acquiring knowledge, beliefs and problem-solving strategies through interaction with what he termed " more knowledgeable others". It is through our interactions with others that we make meaning of the information we encounter. Social learning thus proceeds individual development and is unique.

Vygotsky's socio-cultural theory of language development posits that social interaction plays a crucial role in intellectual development. According to Vygotsky, mental functions are not innate but instead are shaped and influenced by social and cultural context. The role of language is especially important as it serves as a tool for thought and communication to individuals. Vygotsky noticed that as a person develops, he or she uses language in different ways and that the use of speech grows from external cues as a baby to private, inner speech of an adult. As this occurs, the individual is shaped by culture. Vygotsky created three stages of speech and language development: external, egocentric and inner speech. Vygotsky came up with some concepts; More Knowledgeable other (MKO), Zone of proximal Development (ZPD) and Scaffolding.

The Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD)

The zone of Proximal development explains the ability of a learner to extend beyond their own innate ability through interaction with others in their environment. It is the difference between what the learner can achieve independently and what he can learn with the guidance and support of the "more knowledgeable others". Over time, the ZPD expands and grows with the individual learner. More knowledgeable is someone with high level or skills than the learner, as such they serve as source of socio-cultural learning. These more knowledgeable others are always thought of as elderly ones but they can be younger provided they are more experienced or more knowledgeable than the learner.

Scaffolding

This is the assistance offered by the more knowledgeable to take the learner across the zone of proximal development. Teachers, care givers, peers can offer this assistance. Vygotsky came up with a method of guided learning that helps a learner to learn by pairing him with a more knowledgeable other, with his techniques for instructions such as using visual aids, providing examples, working one-on-one with the learner and giving feedback. The aim of scaffolding is to create an environment in which the learner feels comfortable asking questions until they perform the skills without any help.

This theory directly relates to this subject. Vygotsky emphasized the role of culture in the cognitive development of the child. Children use cultural tools to mediate thinking, which in turn help them to solve problems and engage with the world in the ways consistent to their cultures. Language is a tool for cultural transmission. By interacting with learners from different cultural background help in the cognitive development of the learners and build strong bonds in relationships. Cultural background gives children a sense of who they are. The unique cultural influences that children respond to from birth, including customs and beliefs around food, artistic expression and religion affects the children develop emotionally, socially, physically and linguistically.

In the teaching of National Languages and Cultures in primary schools, the teachers, parents and peers are the "more knowledgeable others". The learning activities that the teachers design depends to a higher extent on the attitude, knowledge and beliefs of the teachers. If teachers hold positive beliefs about National Languages and Cultures, their attitudes will be positive and they will use teaching method such as cooperative learning, peer tutoring and involve parents through assignment which provide opportunity for interaction. They will create and use teaching materials that are attractive and motivating such as charts and audio-visual aids. Negative beliefs and poor attitudes towards National Languages and Culture will lead to poor performance. If teachers hold high expectations for learners, their behaviours towards the learners will be such that will enhance an interactive environment for effective learning and hence increase performance. Also, teachers' beliefs are influenced by their cultural backgrounds. Teachers who come from communities that value their language as an aspect of culture will hold positive beliefs and high expectations about their learner's. This will influence their teaching activities positively and hence increase performance. Furthermore, a multilingual classroom having learners from diverse cultural backgrounds will enable children to embrace different learning styles.

The Planned Behaviours Theory by Icek Ajzen (1985-1991)

Planned Behavior theory is a theory used to understand and predict behaviours. It posits that behaviours are immediately determined by behavioural intentions and under certain circumstances perceived behavioural control. Behavioural intentions are determined by a combination of three factors: attitude towards the behaviour, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control. This theory was developed by Icek Ajzen (1985, 1991) as a general model to predict and explain behaviour over a wide range of different types of behaviours. This theory is an extension of the Reason and Act theory which posits that behaviour is a directly predicted by individual behavioural intentions. This means that as an individual's intention to perform a behaviour increases, he is more likely to actually perform that behaviour.

This planned behaviour theory posits that intention are directly predicted by 1) individuals attitude towards the behaviour 2) subjective norms and 3) perceived behavioural control. Attitude refers to an individual's evaluation of a given behaviour. It can be positive or negative. As individuals' attitude become more positive, their intentions to perform a behaviour will increase. Subjective norms are defined as an individual's beliefs about the importance others place on them performing a given behaviour, that is, the degree to which an individual perceives that other people want him to engage in a behaviour. As an individual's subjective norms increase, their intentions to perform a behaviour will increase. Perceived behavioural control encompasses the extent to which an individual believes he has control over performing that behaviour. It should be noted that attitude, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control do not always contribute equally to predict behaviours. Sometimes one of the factors may weigh more than the other. For example, the teacher's intention to teach national languages and cultures may be driven by their attitude towards the subject irrespective of the importance people place on teaching this subject. In the teaching of national languages and cultures, the teacher's intention to teach this subject are driven by their attitude towards the subject, the importance that the government and the community place on the teaching of the subject and their self-efficacy. If the teachers judges the subject as important even if others say otherwise, his intentions to teach the subject will increase and his performance in

the teaching will be improved but if his attitude towards the teaching of the subject is negative, he might teach the subject just to complete the syllabus since it is part of the curriculum and he will put in less effort and hence low performance.

Also, it should be noted that attitude, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control do not always guarantee behaviour. The principle of specificity should be applied to attain the desired outcome. That is, the specific intentions, specific actions, specific context and specific time period should be stated (Rayan M. J., & Worthington, A. k. (2021). So, the teachers need to plan his lessons stating clear objectives and specific time to attain those objectives. This theory gains relevance to this study in that, in the teaching of National Languages and Cultures, the teachers' behaviour in the classroom or during lesson preparation is influenced by his or her attitude towards the subject, the importance that the society places on the teaching of that subject and the ease or difficulty in teaching the subject. If the teacher hold negative attitude towards NLCs, he she will not be effect in teaching this Subject but if his or her attitude is positive, he will do all that it takes to enhance effective learning in the learners. Moreover, if the teachers consider the importance that the society (the Cameroon government, the parents and the educational system) places on NLCS (subjective norms), he will do everything possible to teach this subject effectively but if he undermines the importance of the subject in question, he will not be effective. Also, if the teacher encounters difficulty in teaching this subject which may stem from lack of knowledge in this subject, the teacher will to be effective but if he or she finds it easy to teach the subject, he will be effective (perceived behavioural control).

Statement of the Problem

In Cameroon, the focus on French and English in education has sidelined national languages since colonial times. Although the 1996 constitution and the 1998 law called for the promotion of national languages, it was not implemented until the 2018 New Primary Schools Curriculum that a subject called National Languages and Cultures was introduced, aiming to teach the various indigenous languages and cultures of Cameroon. Effective language teaching methods that enhance interactions, such as cooperative learning, role play and dramatization, dialogue and so on are crucial for language acquisition. Moreover, when a language is effectively taught, it is evident in the learners' ability to express themselves in both written and spoken forms. However, in Douala IV Sub-Division, primary school teachers mainly use the flipped classroom method to teach National Languages and Cultures leading to minimal classroom interaction during NLCS lessons. Learners neither understand, speak, write nor read any national language but only express themselves in English and French both in schools and at home.

If National Languages and Cultures is not effectively taught, there is a risk of language extinction, cultural disconnection, and loss of cultural values. Teachers' perceptions of the subject may significantly impact its teaching effectiveness. Positive attitudes and thorough knowledge are essential for effective teaching. Previous research has explored the use of national languages in instruction and their role in cultural preservation, (Adedigba Soretire & Ajayi 2023) & Nchang 2022), but has rarely focused on teachers' perceptions and teaching methods of National Languages and Cultures. This research aims to fill that gap by investigating the effects of teachers' perceptions on teaching National Languages and Cultures.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the extent to which teachers' attitudes influences the teaching of National languages and Cultures.
2. To find out how teachers' knowledge influences the teaching of National languages and Cultures.
3. To investigate the extent to which teachers' beliefs influences the teaching of National languages and Cultures.

Research Design

This study adopted a mixed method approach to research which involved both quantitative and qualitative methods. The convergent parallel mixed method design was used. It is a type of research in which the researcher collects both qualitative and quantitative data separately, analyze them separately to find out if the findings confirm or disconfirm each other. This design was chosen because of its ability to give an accurate result from different sources of data. For quantitative research, descriptive survey design was used. This design involves gathering vast data from a heterogeneous audience. The survey design method involves questions relevant to the subject of the research. The survey questions or questionnaires are then distributed to the audience with the hope of receiving their honest answers. The descriptive survey research design was chosen because they are easier and cost efficient compared to other research designs. Also, they can be conducted online or offline and can be distributed through many different channels. This research design is also a reliable method of inquiry because they are standardized in that the same questions phrased exactly in the same words are used to all participants thereby limiting.

Sample Size

This is the actual portion of the population of study to which the researcher administers his or her instruments. The sample comprised of a total number of 69 teachers who were obtained purposively by taking all the teachers of 11 schools to make up the sample size. This method gave almost every teacher a chance of being selected. The sample size

was drawn from the accessible population using a scientific formula (Slovin, 1960). Using this formula helped to select the accurate sample size which is the representative of the population of the study. The formula is: $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$

Where n=sample size

N=the finite population (the population whose number is known) e=level of significant (limit of tolerable error)

1=unity (constant)

Based on the formula above, the sample size is calculated as follows: $N=83, e=0.05 n = \frac{83}{1 + 83(0.05)^2} = 68.87 = 69$

Table 1

Distribution of sample size

SCHOOLS	NUMBER OF TEACHERS
GEPS Bojongo	5
GEPS Nkonjibe 1	3
GEPS Bonassama	6
GEPS Ndobu 1A	7
GEPS Ndobu 11A	9
GEPS Ndobu 11B	6
GEPS Bonandale	6
GEPS Mabanda	7
GEPS Bonamatoumbe	7
GEPS Ngwelle	7
GEPS Sodiko Royal	6
Total	69

Sampling Technique

The accessible population was selected purposively due to the fact that some schools did not have a complete staff so the researcher selected schools with the highest number of staff. This entails selecting respondents who satisfy some determined criteria. The sample size for quantitative data was also selected purposively by taking all the teachers from 11 schools and 3 teachers from one school in order to make up the required number for the sample size. This makes the sample more representative of the population of study. The sample for qualitative data was obtained through chain referral or snow ball sampling.

Findings

Research Question One: To what extent does Teachers' attitudes Towards NLCs influence its teaching?

The focus here was to examine the effects of teachers' attitudes on the teaching of National Languages and Cultures English Primary schools in Douala IV Sub-Division.

Table 2

Distribution according to the effects of Teachers attitudes on the teaching of NLCs

Items	Stretched				Collapsed		Decision
	SA	A	SD	D	SA/A	D/SD	
Teaching a language that you don't know is frustrating	47 (78.3)	13 (21.7)	00 (0.0%)	00 (0.0%)	60 (100%)	00 (0.0%)	Agree
I fill discourage when it comes to teaching NLCs in a multilingual classroom	13 (21.7)	40 (66.7)	05 (8.3%)	02 (3.3%)	53 (88.3)	07 (11.7)	Agree
I feel that NLCs should be taught by an expert	26 (43.3)	22 (36.7)	05 (8.3%)	07 (11.7)	48 (80.0)	12 (20.0)	Agree
I feel embarrassed when I don't understand my learners' languages	16 (26.7)	35 (58.3)	05 (8.3%)	04 (6.7%)	51 (85.0)	09 (15.0)	Agree
Teaching NLCS is a waste of time because it is not evaluated in the FSLC exams	05 (8.3%)	14 (23.3)	19 (31.7)	22 (36.7)	19 (31.7)	41 (68.3) %	Disagree

I hesitate to evaluate learners in NLCs because I can't tell if all their answers are correct.	08 (13.3)	42 (70.0)	07 (11.7)	03 (5.0%)	50 (88.3)	10 (11.7)	Agree
MRS	115 (31.9)	166 (46.1)	41 (11.9)	38 (10.6)	281 (78.1)	79 (21.9)	Agree

Table 2 above presents teachers' attitudes and its influence on the Teaching of National Languages and Cultures in English Primary schools. The general score across all items (78.1%) indicates that respondents confirmed that teachers' attitudes influence the teaching of national languages and cultures. All the respondents 100% perceived that teachers feel frustrated when teaching the language they do not know. A majority of the respondent (88.7%) feel discouraged when it comes to teaching NLCs in a multilingual classroom with 11.7% feeling otherwise. Also, most respondents (85.0%) agreed that NLCs should be taught by experts whilst 15% disagreed. Again, most respondents (85.3%) are highly embarrassed when they do not understand the learners' languages. Many teachers (68.3%) highly perceived that the teaching of NLCS was not a waste of time although it is not being evaluated in the FSLC exams while 31.7% did not think so. Similarly, most respondents (83.3%) highly perceived that teachers hesitate to evaluate learners in NLCs because they are never sure if their answers are correct. The figure below presents the overall opinion from participants.

Table 3

Testing the influence of teachers' attitude on the Teaching of national languages and cultures in primary schools

Test	Statistics	Teachers' attitude	Teaching of NLCs
Spearman's rho	R-value	1.000	.275**
	P-value	.	.000
	N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Statistically, findings showed that teachers' attitude significantly predict the Teaching of national languages and cultures in primary schools ($P = 0.000$; <0.05). The positive sign of the correlation ($R = 0.347^{**}$) implied that the teaching of National Languages and Cultures is more likely to witness significant influence from teachers' attitude towards the subject. Therefore, the null hypothesis that teachers' attitudes do not influence the teaching of national languages and cultures in primary schools was rejected, whilst the alternate hypothesis that teachers' attitudes influence the teaching of national languages and cultures in English primary schools was retained.

Table 4

Respondents' opinion on how teachers' attitudes influence the teaching of National Languages and culture in primary schools

Question	Themes	Quotations
Teachers' opinions on teaching NLCs	Difficulty "Difficult to teach because pupils come from due to different tribes and cultures" diverse "Classroom management is too difficult because the linguistic children are learning different languages and cultures in the same classroom guided by one teacher." backgrounds	"I am afraid I "unteach" them as I don't know their languages and at times, I try to teach them my own dialect" "Difficulty to teach without text books and peer learning teacher is not sure they are doing the right thing"

Discouraged
 Boring curriculum
 Reluctant and uncertainty

“I am sometimes frustrated as I don't really know how to go about teaching what I don't know. Classroom management is too difficult because the children are learning different languages and cultures in the same classroom guided by one teacher.”

Teachers’ feeling on the teaching of NLCs

“Pupils comes from different tribes with different languages and I don't understand their languages. So, it boring to me.”

“It's boring because only few pupils participate and some times it seems as if am forcing my own dialects to the pupils. Some pupils even understand their dialect more than me the teacher”

“Only a few pupils participate and sometimes it seems as if am forcing my own dialects to the pupils.” “I feel reluctant to teach this subject because it is Difficult to even learn all the languages of the learners. More to that there are no textbooks or teaching guide to help us. Even with the flip classroom method, you don't even know if the peers are teaching the right thing.

Research Question Two: To what extent does Teachers’ Knowledge of NLCs influence its teaching?

The focus here was on examining how teachers’ knowledge affects the teaching of National Languages and Cultures in English Primary School in Douala IV Sub-Division.

Table 1
Distribution according to the effects of teachers’ knowledge on the teaching of NLCs

ITEMS	Stretched				Collapsed		Decision
	SA	A	SD	D	SA/A	D/SD	
I am aware of the introduction of NLCs in the Primary school curriculum	38 (63.3)	22 (36.7)	00 (0.0%)	00 (0.0%)	60 (100%)	00 (0.0%)	Agree
I have a copy of the new curriculum	24 (40.0)	30 (50.0)	04 (6.7%)	02 (3.3%)	54 (90.0)	06 (10.0)	Agree
I don’t understand all my pupils’ languages	20 (33.3)	36 (60.0)	02 (3.3%)	02 (3.3%)	56 (93.3)	04 (6.7%)	Agree
I don’t master the teaching methods and strategies for NLCs	08 (13.3)	36 (60.0)	08 (13.3)	08 (13.3)	44 (73.3)	16 (26.7)	Agree
I have received training on the teaching of NLCs in a multilingual class	02 (3.3%)	13 (21.7)	16 (26.7)	29 (48.3)	15 (25.0)	45 (75.0)	Disagree
I Face problems evaluating learners because I don’t understand their languages	14 (23.3)	39 (65%)	04 (6.7%)	03 (5.0%)	53 (88.3%)	07 (11.7%)	Agree
Multiple Response Set (MRS)	106 (29.4)	176 (48.9)	34 (9.4%)	44 (12.2)	282 (78.3)	78 (21.7)	Agree

Table 5 above presents data on how teachers' knowledge influences the Teaching of National Languages and Cultures in English Primary schools. The multiple response set scores had a majority 78.3 % accepting that teachers' knowledge influences the teaching of National Languages and Cultures in English Primary schools. All the respondents 100% are aware that NLCs have been introduced in the Primary school curriculum. A majority of the respondent (90.0%) have a copy of the new curriculum whilst a few (10.0%) do not have a copy. Furthermore, a majority of respondents (93.3%) accepted that teachers do not understand all their pupils' languages and a minority 6.7% disagreed. Also, most respondents (73.3%) accepted that teachers do not master the teaching methods and strategies for NLCs, but a few 26.7% disagreed. For the training of teachers' on NLCs, most teachers (75.0%) indicated not to have received training on the teaching of NLCs in a multilingual class. Moreso, many teachers (88.3%) indicated they face problems evaluating learners given that they do not understand the language of the learners. The figure below presents the overall opinion from participants.

Table 6**Testing the influence of teachers' knowledge on the teaching of national languages and cultures in primary schools**

Test	Statistics	Teachers' Knowledge	Teaching of NLCs
Spearman's rho	R-value	1.000	0.242**
	P-value	.	.000
	N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Statistically, findings showed that teachers' knowledge significantly predict the teaching of national languages and cultures in English primary schools ($P = 0.000$; <0.05). The positive sign of the correlation ($R = 0.242^{**}$) implied that the teaching of national languages and cultures is likely to witness significant influence from the teachers' knowledge. Therefore, the null hypothesis that teachers' knowledge does not influence the teaching of national languages and cultures was rejected, whilst the alternate hypothesis that teachers' knowledge influences the teaching of national languages and cultures was maintained.

Table 7**Respondents' opinion on how teachers' knowledge influences the teaching of National Languages and culture in primary schools**

Question	Themes	Quotations
What do you know about the teaching of National Languages and Cultures?	Non mastery of content and inadequate teaching methods and strategies	<i>"I only know that I have the curriculum but I don't master it's content. I don't even know that national language content not to talk of knowing the teaching methods and strategies. I know that pictures, charts and audios or video can help but it's still not easy."</i> <i>"The only method of teaching so far that I know is the flip classroom method which is not effective especially when I can tell if the children are learning the right thing from their peers."</i>
What training have you obtained so far concerning the teaching of national Languages and Culture?	Lack of training on the teaching of NLCs	<i>"No formal training on the teaching of NLCs. Few seminars are organised but are inadequate. The inservice pedagogic seminars are not sufficient enough to equip teachers the knowledge requires to teach NLCs in primary schools."</i>

Research Question three: To what extent does teachers' beliefs on National Languages and Culture influence its teaching?

The focus here was to find out the extent to which teachers' beliefs influence the teaching of National Languages and cultures in English Primary schools in Douala IV Sub-Division.

ITEMS	Stretched				Collapsed		
	SA	A	SD	A	SA/A	D/SD	Decision
NLCS is very important for the socio-cultural development	41 (68.3 %)	19 (31.7 %)	00 (0.0%)	00 (0.0%)	60 (100%)	00 (0.0%)	Agree

of a child							
I believe that every native language is important to its people	30 (50.0%)	30 (50.0%)	00 (0.0%)	00 (0.0%)	60 (100%)	00 (0.0%)	Agree
I am confident in my content knowledge of NLCs	02 (3.3%)	24 (40.0%)	17 (28.3%)	17 (28.3%)	26 (43.3%)	34 (56.6%)	Disagree
I am confident of my ability to teach NLCS in a multilingual class effectively	01 (1.7%)	13 (21.7%)	31 (51.7%)	15 (25.0%)	14 (23.3%)	46 (76.7%)	Agree
I believe that pupils will learn better with appropriate teaching materials	15 (25.0%)	35 (58.3%)	3 (5.0%)	07 (11.7%)	50 (83.3%)	10 (16.7%)	Agree
I believe that pupils will learn better if taught by an expert	17 (28.3%)	30 (50.0%)	09 (15.0%)	04 (6.7%)	47 (78.3%)	13 (21.7%)	Agree
Multiple Response Set (MRS)	106 (31.9)	151 (46.1)	60 (11.9)	43 (10.6)	257 (71.4)	103 (28.6)	Agree

Table 8 above presents information how teachers' beliefs influence the teaching of National Languages and Cultures in English Primary schools. The overall score across all items indicated 71.4% of respondents accepting that primary school teachers' beliefs influence the teaching of national languages and cultures with a few 28.6% disagreeing. All the teachers, 100%, agreed with that NLCS are very important for the socio-cultural development of a child. Again, all the respondents (100%) that every native language is important to its people. A majority of the respondents (56.6%), opined that teachers are not confident in their content knowledge of NLCs. A majority of the respondents (76.7%) are not confident in their ability to teach NLCs effectively in multilingual classes. Many respondents, (83.3%) had the conviction that pupils learn better with appropriate teaching materials. The figure below presents the overall opinion from participants.

Table 9

Testing the influence of teachers' beliefs on the teaching of national languages and cultures in primary schools

Test	Statistics	Teachers' Beliefs	Teaching of NLCs
Spearman's rho	R-value	1.000	0.903**
	P-value	.000	
	N	60	60

**** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

Statistically, findings showed that teacher's belief significantly predict the teaching of national languages and cultures in English primary schools ($P = 0.000; < 0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation ($R = 0.903^{**}$) implied that the teaching of national languages and cultures is likely to witness significant influence from the teachers' beliefs. Therefore, the null

hypothesis that teachers' beliefs does not influence the teaching of national languages and cultures was rejected, whilst the alternate hypothesis that teachers' beliefs influence the teaching of national languages and cultures was maintained.

Table 10

Respondents' opinion on how teachers' beliefs influence the teaching of National Languages and culture in primary schools

Questions	Themes	Quotations
Do you believe that National Languages and Cultures is an important subject?	Very essential for social integration and acquisition of lifelong learning skills	<i>“Cultures indicates human identity, whilst national languages help children to communicate easily with each other, learn from peers and easily integrate in the society.”</i> <i>“The multicultural nature of Cameroon, enable pupils to interact with others from diverse backgrounds, consequently enhancing the acquisition of lifelong learning skills”.</i>
Can you effectively teach this subject in a multilingual classroom?	Ineffective	<i>“It is practically impossible. We are not trained on the teaching of NLCs. Teaching materials and textbooks not available. How can you teach what you don't know?”</i>

Discussion of Findings

Teachers' attitudes and the Teaching of National Languages and Cultures

The effects of teachers' attitudes on the teaching of NLCS were examined and findings reveal that teachers' attitudes towards the teaching of NLCs has significant effects on its teaching. Teachers appreciate the importance of National Languages and Cultures as a means to create cultural awareness and build a sense of identity however they manifest negative attitudes towards the teaching of this subject. A positive teachers' attitude toward teaching enhances effective teaching by fostering a classroom environment that is motivating, interactive and learners friendly while a negative teachers' attitude inhibits effective teaching because teachers will not care to create a learner centered environment that support effective teaching and learning. From teachers' opinions, negative attitude toward these subject stems from lack of knowledge of subject matter, lack of training, lack of textbooks and the multilingual nature of the class. When a teacher lacks knowledge of subject, it develops lack of self-confidence and this lack of self-confidence brings discouragement. These findings tie with the work of Owusu (2021) which reveals that knowledge of subject matter of curriculum that teachers are required to teach influence their attitude. Sun (2017) states that lack of knowledge of subject matter can lead to frustration. When a teacher lacks knowledge of subject matter, it leads to low self-esteem. According to Russel (1971) as cited by David (2013) talking about attitude promotion, he mentioned that one of the motivational bases for attitude formation is value expression. To him, value expression attitude is based on one's self-esteem and self-actualization.

“People seek to develop an identity on the concept of self-esteem which they have pride.” This implies that attitude that coincide with a person's values and ego-ideals will enhance one's feeling of self-esteem. The majority of the teachers exhibit negative attitudes towards NLCs because of low self-esteem attached to the subject. Teachers give complains such as; “it's boring, it's discouraging because I don't understand my learners' languages”, “I feel as if am un-teaching the learner”. These statements indicate low self-esteem on the part of the teacher. Negative attitude of teachers towards subject demotivates the teacher and a demotivated teacher cannot motivate learners. This confirms the opinion of Rugayat & Rashidat (2015) who states that negative attitude towards one's job affects how he or she plans and prepares his or her lessons. He further states that teachers' attitude be it consciously or unconsciously greatly affects students' performance because his attitude influences students' interest in learning. If a teacher appears not to be interested or careful about a particular subject, he or she will be unable to create a learning environment that fosters learning.

Furthermore, teachers' attitudes towards the teaching of NLCs greatly influence their expectations of learners' achievement. Teachers stated that only few learners participate indicating low expectation on learners' performance. Bell & Gilbert (1996) assert that teachers' attitudes and beliefs also influence their expectations oof how their teaching can effectively help students to learn which in turn affect their attitudes towards the instructional process. When a teachers feels bored or as if he/she is “unteaching” the learners, his/her expectation about learners' performance will be low. On the other hand, positive attitudes' leads to high expectations which push teachers to put more efforts which can result to high performance. More so, teachers revealed that the multilingual nature of the classroom makes classroom management difficult. Negative attitudes influence classroom management. Classroom management is one of the most challenging things that teachers have to deal with. Although teachers often receive pre and in-service training on

classroom management, studies reveal that classroom management decisions are significantly affected by teachers' attitudes and beliefs (Parker, 2004, Garret, 2005).

Moreover, findings reveal that most teachers feel that this subject should be taught by experts. An expert is someone with specialized knowledge in a subject. This specialized knowledge develops through back ground knowledge during secondary and high school education and not during professional training. NLCs is a new subject and so no teacher has specialized knowledge on all the languages and culture of their learners. This lack of knowledge of subject matter turns to demotivate teachers thereby resulting to negative attitudes towards the teaching of this subject. Kind (2009) asserts that teachers who teach within their specialization develop self-confidence and can identify students' difficulties as compared to those who teach subjects outside their specialization.

Findings also reveal that teachers face problems evaluating learners. Evaluation helps check the understanding level and level of achievement of learners. It also reveals the areas of difficulties of the learners and permits the teachers to use other approaches and strategies to enhance understanding. Evaluation tells if the learning objectives have been attained, it also tests the effectiveness of the teaching methods and strategies (Shinde 2022). When a teacher cannot evaluate effectively, it clearly indicates that s/he cannot teach effectively. Findings tie with those of Jamaluddin & Abdullah (2013) who revealed that teachers' attitudes towards the teaching have significant direct effects on their professional performance. This corroborates with the planned behaviour theory of Ajzen Icek (1991) which states that behavioural intentions are influenced by attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control. The teachers' negative attitudes towards NLCs negatively influence their intentions to teach the subject while positive attitudes influence their intentions positively and fosters effective teaching.

These findings also tie with the self-perception theory of Daryl Bem which states that individuals infer their attitudes and beliefs by observing their behaviours and the circumstances surrounding the behaviour. The teacher will understand that he or she has a negative attitude towards NLCs by observing his behaviour during lessons and the circumstances surrounding the behaviour. This can help the teacher to modify his behaviour in order to build an attitude that foster learning.

Teachers' Knowledge and the teaching of NLCs

The effects of teachers' knowledge on the teaching of National Languages and Cultures were examined and findings revealed that teachers' knowledge has a significant effect on the teaching of National Languages and Cultures. The majority of the teachers agree that they are aware of the introduction of NLCs into the Primary school curriculum. Also, nearly all the teachers agreed that they possess the new curriculum. Curriculum according to Tanner and Tanner (1980) as cited by Mulenga (2018) is "the planned and guided learning experiences and intended learning outcomes formulated through the systematic reconstruction of knowledge and experiences, under the auspices of school for the learners' continuous and willful growth in personal social competence". Even though the curriculum specifies the content, specific learning outcomes, suggested methodology and didactic materials, this study also revealed that in addition to the lack of knowledge of subject matter, teachers also lack pedagogic content knowledge in this subject.

Subject matter knowledge is knowledge of content. It refers to knowledge in disciplines taught by the teacher. When teachers are assigned to teach out of their expertise, they struggle in their decisions about how to present the content and how to consider students' understanding Luft (2020). This is exactly what teachers are facing in the teaching of NLCs. National Languages and Cultures has just been introduced in the teachers' training program perhaps this may help improve the subject matter knowledge of the teacher.

Pedagogic content knowledge refers to knowledge that integrates content of specific subject and pedagogical knowledge for teaching that subject (Shulman 1987) as cited by Mulenga (2018). This pedagogic content knowledge involves knowledge of units to be taught within a specific period of time, knowledge of teaching methods and strategies, knowledge of evaluation strategies, knowledge of relevant teaching material, classroom arrangement and many more. In short, it embodies all that it takes to effectively teach the subject in question. According to Zhoa (2022), pedagogic knowledge is obtained through training and from collaboration with colleagues. Teachers disagree to have received training on the teaching of this subject. Without professional training, any teacher who teaches any subject is regarded as an amateur. He cannot teach effectively and this applies also to the teaching of NLCS. Training makes the difference between a native who speaks and writes a language and a professional teacher of that language.

These findings confirm what Ulfert (2022) opined that effective teachers are not only expert of subject matter but also of how students learn, how to assess learning progress and how to design learning experiences for students. These findings also reveal that teachers face difficulties in evaluating their learners and these difficulties are rooted in their lack of knowledge of the subject matter and lack of pedagogic knowledge. As earlier mentioned, evaluation plays a crucial role

on the teaching and learning process. It tests learning progress, guides instructions and helps in decision making. Being unable to evaluate learners indicates lack of pedagogic content knowledge which inhibits effective teaching.

Contribution to Educational Psychology

The findings of this study reveal that teachers' perceptions have significant effects on the teaching of national languages and cultures. The major contribution of this study to educational psychology is that it brings out the Afro-centric literature on the effects of teacher's attitudes, knowledge and beliefs on the teaching of National Languages and Cultures in Cameroon Primary school and Douala IV Sub-Division in particular.

By examining teachers' attitudes towards the teaching of NLCs, this study will provide insight into the factors that influence their perceptions. This include exploring how personal beliefs, professional training, teaching materials and cultural background shape their views on the importance and implementation of this subject's curriculum.

By linking teachers' perceptions to learners' outcome, this study will provide evidence on how positive attitudes towards National Languages and Cultures education can enhance pupils' engagement, cultural awareness and academic performance. This will underscore the importance of this subject in the overall educational experiences.

The findings of this study will have important implications for educational policy and curriculum development. By providing a comprehensive understanding of teachers' perceptions and the factors that influence them, the study will inform policy makers on how to better support teachers and promote the teaching of NLCs in schools. This contribution will not only add to the academic discourse but also provide practical recommendations for educators, schools leaders and policy makers to enhance the teaching and learning of National Languages and Cultures in Cameroon Primary schools.

It has further revealed the critical importance of teachers' perception in teaching. Negative attitudes, lack of knowledge and negative beliefs leads to poor planning, poor preparation of learning environment and hence ineffective teaching whereas, positive attitudes, availability of knowledge and positive beliefs leads to good planning, good preparation of an enabling environment that foster learning leading to effective teaching. By understanding the impact that their attitudes have on the teaching of National languages and cultures, teachers engage a change in behaviour that will produce attitudes that foster effective teaching.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of the study, the following recommendations were made:

Pedagogic animators for basic education should sensitize teachers on the effects of teachers' perceptions on the teaching of National Languages and Cultures so that they can make the necessary adjustment on their attitudes and beliefs needed for the effective teaching of this subject.

The educational policy makers and curriculum developers and the ministry of basic education should organize and sponsor special training programs the will enhance teachers professional development in the subject so that teachers could gain the appropriate knowledge needed for the teaching of this subject.

The Ministry of basic education should include National Languages and Cultures in the First School Leaving Certificate Examinations. This will permit the educational system to evaluate performance of pupils in this subject. Evaluation of this subject in official examination will push the school authorities to lay strong emphasis which will compel teachers to value the subject and hence change their perceptions towards the subject for effective teaching.

Conclusion

The ineffective teaching of National languages and Cultures is a call for concern. This is the reason why this study sought to investigate the effects of teachers' perceptions on the teaching of National Languages and Cultures in English Primary schools in Douala IV Sub-Division., specifically, the study sought to investigate the effects of teachers' attitudes, teachers' knowledge and teachers' beliefs on the teaching of National Languages and Cultures. The perceptions of teachers towards the teaching of National Languages and Cultures play a crucial role in shaping educational outcomes. Positive perceptions can lead to more enthusiastic and effective teaching practices, fostering a deeper appreciation and understanding of cultural heritage among students. When teachers value and actively promote National Languages and Cultures, they contribute to the preservation and promotion of cultural identity and linguistic diversity.

Conversely, negative perceptions or lack of emphasis on this subject can result to diminishing student interest and engagement, potentially leading to erosion of cultural knowledge and language skills. It is essential for policy makers and leaders to recognize the impact of teachers' attitudes towards the teaching of this subject and provide necessary support and professional development to enhance the perceptions and teaching practices. By fostering a supportive environment and emphasizing the importance of National Languages and Cultures, we can ensure that these vital aspects of education

are effectively integrated into the curriculum benefiting both the teachers and students. This approach does not only enrich the educational experiences but also strengthen the cultural fabrics of the society.

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